

EOSC-hub

Evaluation of the EOSC-hub community (February 2020)

Abstract

The EOSC-hub project operates many of the core elements of the European Open Science Cloud, and acts as an important facilitator of onboarding providers, users and communities to the EOSC Portal. This document provides a snapshot about the different stakeholders that have been engaged by EOSC-hub until February 2020. The document presents our assessment of the engaged communities from different perspectives: instrument that was used for the engagement; role in the EOSC ecosystem; geographical distribution; science discipline affiliation. Based on the findings we provide recommendations that can help the project strengthen community engagement activities for its remaining lifetime.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/EOSC-hub+Glossary>

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1. Introduction

Task 3.2 of EOSC-hub is responsible for community engagement. Task 3.2 provides oversight of engagement work with communities that are already represented in the consortium within other WPs, and does proactive engagement with new communities who we should engage with for the success of the project. This proactive engagement uses various instruments that the project setup during its 2 years.

This document provides a snapshot about the communities that have been engaged by EOSC-hub until February 2020, with the ultimate goal to support engagement activities for the rest of the project. In the document we perform assessment of the engaged communities, the engagement instruments and make recommendations that can help the project strengthen community engagement and its impact for the remaining period. Data for this report was pulled together by the T3.2 team from

- WP7 and WP8 WPs (Thematic services and Competence centres)
- JIRA project used to track service onboarding
- Early adopter programme applications
- Stakeholder Database (tracking early adoptions)
- Strategy board membership
- JIRA project used to track service orders (access requests)

Our assessment covers engagement with 155 communities, reached with the following instruments:

- **Competence centres:** WP8 includes 8 competence centres (CCs) since the start of the project. These CCs link to **10** research infrastructure communities. These communities carry out technology and service assessment activities with the ultimate goal of setting up new 'thematic services' designed for specific research infrastructure communities.
- **Thematic services:** WP7 includes **9** Thematic Service provider communities since the start of the project. These 9 communities deliver science discipline specific services to researchers via the EOSC-hub channels, and gradually expand the functionality of these services by integrating them with generic e-infrastructure and access enabling services of the project.
- **Service providers onboarded:** Communities can apply to become service providers in EOSC since November 2018, when the EOSC Portal was launched. The EOSC-hub project onboarded **35** new communities until now. (There have been 85 services added to EOSC by EOSC-hub in total. These are provided by members of the consortium, such as CCs and TSs, and by these 35 newly engaged provider communities.)
- **Early adopter Programme pilots (EaP):** The project launched two calls for 'Early adopters' in 2019. The selected Early adopters receive technical support and infrastructure services with capacity from the project to integrate science discipline specific use cases and applications into EOSC. **13** EaPs have been selected: 5 in the 1st and 8 in the 2nd call.
- **Event engagement:** The project continuously seeks for external events where our services and support can be promoted for new communities, and engagement with new communities can be established. There are **4** communities at the moment in our engagement pipeline. Initial discussion took place with these communities at external

events, and we are in the process of further discussing collaboration and eventually moving them into becoming service users, providers, supporters. (Several already onboarded service provider and user also started with ‘event engagement’)

- **Strategy board:** The project runs a strategy board where the 5 ESFRI Cluster projects have 1-1 representatives. This arrangement is also considered as a form of engagement and is included in our assessment.
- **Users via the Marketplace:** Until the time of writing 82 unique users submitted 194 access requests in total via the EOSC-hub Marketplace that is linked to the EOSC Portal. Despite the engagement with such users is a much lighter type of engagement than any of the above described ones, we still consider it as a useful input to our landscape analysis.

2. Analysis of long-term engagement

In this section we look at the communities that have been engaged with the long term engagement instruments, i.e. considering all the instruments, but the ‘Users via the Marketplace’. There are 73 communities considered in this analysis.

2.1 Analysis by the engagement instrument

The following pie chart shows the split of communities by engagement instrument, considering the long term engagement instruments (i.e. all but the ‘Users via the Marketplace’):

Fig 1. Classification of engaged communities by the Type of engagement instruments we used

From the chart it can be observed that:

- the Service provider engagement became the main instrument, nearly outweighing all other instruments together.
- The pace at which services are onboarded shows an increasing trend, so we will see an even stronger dominance of service provider onboarding by the end of 2020. The event engagement shows a small number, but only because it reflects the number of communities who are currently considered as 'contacts we made an external event'. Many of the communities who signed up as service providers or became users or applicants of EaP pilot also encountered EOSC-hub via an event - so this engagement instrument is still impactful despite its share of the pie.
- We think that the Early adopter Programme can be also considered a success, because we received 12 responses to the 1st, 15 responses to the 2nd call.

2.1 Analysis by stakeholder role

Figure 2 shows the classification of engaged communities by the role they play in the EOSC-hub landscape. We distinguish user communities (users of the generic services), provider communities (meaning from academia), providers from industry, communities that play a dual role (they consume generic services and provide thematic services), and strategy board members. The main messages from this analysis:

1. The project onboarded already 10 providers from industry.
2. ~2/3rd of the engaged communities act as providers. This is insync with the previous figure. (because there Service Providers, Thematic Services, some of the CCs and some of the EaP pilots are also providers)
3. The user communities on this diagram do not show the complete picture. The number should be complemented with those users who requested access to services via the EOSC Marketplace (82, more than this pie in total).

Fig 2. Classification of engaged communities by the role they play in/with the project

2.2 Analysis by geographical type

Our next analysis looked at the classification of engaged communities by their geographical footprint. We used the following options:

- Global: The community has members from Europe and elsewhere
- European: The community has a dominant presence in Europe. ESFRIs are typical examples.
- Multi-national: The community has presence in several European countries, but without a major goal to expand its footprint.
- National: The community/stakeholder is present in one country.

The data confirms the focus of EOSC-hub on international/multi-national communities, however there is already a good share of approx 25% by national communities. We expect this share to grow gradually by the end of the project as a result of onboarding of new providers by the national EOSC projects (funded under the INFRAEOSC05b call). Our current analysis does not go into the level of where the national communities so far came from - because we expect a dynamic change in this picture. (We provide an analysis of the nationality of users later.)

Count of Geographical type

Fig 3. Classification of engaged communities by their geographical footprint

2.3 Analysis of science discipline distribution

We believe that the most important analysis of our community engagement is by the scientific disciplines. We used the "REVISED FIELD OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (FOS) CLASSIFICATION IN THE FRASCATI MANUAL"¹ to classify the engaged communities by their science discipline. This classification scheme is the basis of classification used by EGI and EUDAT. We used the classification up to 2 levels. The 1st level classification is shown in Fig 4.

Count of Discipline 1st level

Fig 4. Classification of engaged communities by their science discipline (1st level)

¹ <http://unstats.un.org/unsd/EconStatKB/Attachment332.aspx?AttachmentType=1>

From the pie we can observe that:

- Natural sciences dominate (35 communities): This is due to the fact that the classification we used pulls physical, chemical, earth, biological sciences under a single top level class. Because of this we zoom into this slice in the next diagram and its related analysis.
- The ‘engineering and technology’ domain has a big share (23 communities): This is because generic services (such as HTC, cloud, data management) has no better place to be in the classification we used and because the EOSC-hub consortium is dominated by such providers.
- Medical sciences have ‘only’ 6 communities. This is because under the ‘Natural sciences’ there is also a ‘Biological sciences’ subdiscipline so the two should be considered together. (See later)
- Social sciences and humanities have 7+2 communities together. This is an area where EOSC-hub should probably increase its outreach.

Our next analysis (Fig 5) goes into the details of the Natural sciences discipline (following the classification schema we chose - See above). From this pie chart we can observe:

- A big dominance of earth science communities (18) is due to the fact that the TSs and CCs have a very high number from this domain. There were only a few that joined later, as EaP pilot or as service provider via the EOSC Portal.
- The low number of physics science communities (6), given that EOSC-hub has strong drive by EGI and EUDAT, e-infrastructures that are strongly linked to physics communities.
- 14 biology communities is probably a bit under-representation (5 here and 6 in the first level as ‘medical sciences’ and 3 in the first level as ‘agricultural sciences’).

Natural sciences communities per sub-discipline

Fig 5. Classification of Natural science communities by their 2nd level discipline

3. Analysis of engagement via the Portal and Marketplace

Our next analysis looks at the visits in the EOSC Portal and Marketplace, and at the service access requests (alias 'orders') from the EOSC Marketplace. On Fig 6 we present the monthly visits on the EOSC Portal and on the Marketplace, on Fig 7 the number of service access orders received each month via the Marketplace.

The graphs on Fig 6 do not show any clear trend: After the initial opening of the EOSC Portal and Marketplace the visits dropped (understandably), and although there was a 50% increase in visits since Sept 2019 it is still early to say whether it is start of an increasing trend, whether the number will stabilise at this level, or it will go back to a lower level.

From Fig 7 we observe that there is 5-15 orders per month, with the exception of two months. In July 2019 we received a large number of orders from Korea from a single user (who turned out to be only testing the Marketplace). In January 2020 several users requested services - We are yet to see whether the orders stabilise to this higher level, or it was a one-time peak.

Fig 6. Number of visits on the EOSC Portal and Marketplace per month

Fig 7. Number of service access orders received via the Marketplace per month

Table 1 below presents details on the received orders. The data is shown in two columns: Total number of orders, and total number of users who submitted those orders. This distinction is important because - as it can be seen from the data - some users submitted many orders. While sometimes these orders make sense (when e.g. a storage service and compute service are requested in one go), sometimes the orders are mistakes, misunderstanding, tests or violation of policies (quite visibly from Korea).

The main observations are:

- Germany, UK, Poland and France are the most active. (This inline with their proportion of population)
- There was 1 Korean user who submitted a lot of requests.
- Considering EU members and associated countries we did not receive any access request from: Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Estonia, Ireland, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Montenegro, Macedonia, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Turkey.
→ The project should definitely strengthen presence in these countries.

Table 1. Origin of service access requests (user orders in the EOOSC-hub Marketplace)

User's country	Total orders	Unique users
Albania	2	1
Armenia	2	1
Australia	2	2
Austria	4	3
Belgium	1	1
Brazil	1	1
Czech Republic	1	1

Denmark	4	2
EU projects	4	3
Finland	2	2
France	26	8
Germany	36	22
Greece	2	2
Hungary	2	2
Italy	6	3
Korea	52	2
Netherlands	5	3
Poland	12	6
Slovenia	2	1
Spain	4	2
Sweden	5	4
Switzerland	1	1
United Kingdom	18	9
TOTAL	194	82

4. Gap analysis and recommendations

We consider science discipline outreach as an important measure of success. Table 2. maps the number of already engaged communities into the complete discipline hierarchy classification scheme we used in this report. The analysis points out the disciplines with no engagement so far, allowing the project to focus on finding and attending events specific to those disciplines. Engagement in certain disciplines can be also strengthened via the science discipline specific projects, e.g. the ESFRI clusters, or INFRAEOSC02/05b projects that work with certain disciplines. We should continue seeking for additional conferences to cover the whole spectrum of disciplines.

There are many European countries from which EOSC did not service service access requests (See Section 3 above). There is an urgent need to strengthen outreach in those countries, and the project should do this by relying on national peers, e.g. national OpenAIRE workshops and INFRAEOSC05b regional EOSC projects.

The number of visits on the EOSC Website and EOSC Marketplace show a constant traffic. The project - and other projects and stakeholders on the EOSC landscape - have to invest more effort and more coordinated effort into disseminating the EOSC Portal if we want to see the number of visits to increase. EOSC-Secretariat could make a coordinated effort here (and possibly fund a short project in this area from its co-creation budget).

Despite the number of services in the EOSC Marketplace is continuously growing, the number of orders submitted via the Marketplace does not increase (except in the last month). On one hand this

is because the number of visitors also stagnate. But on the other hand it can be an indication that the service offer via the EOSC Portal and Marketplace is still not attractive enough for users to come and request access. The project should increase the speed at which services are published. On one hand this can be achieved by reallocating people to the service publishing team from other activities (there are ~15 services ready for publishing but only 1-2 services are published per month). The project should also work more closely with potential service providers and provider projects to feed new services into the onboarding pipeline.

Table 2. Gap analysis: Disciplines with engaged communities vs. non-engagement

LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	COUNT
1. Natural sciences	1.1 Mathematics	0
	1.2 Computer and information sciences	1
	1.3 Physical sciences	8
	1.4 Chemical sciences	2
	1.5 Earth and related Environmental sciences	18
	1.6 Biological sciences	7
	1.7 Other natural sciences	0
	Total	36
2. Engineering and Technology	2.1 Civil Engineering	0
	2.2 Electrical engineering, Electronic engineering, Information engineering	1
	2.3 Mechanical engineering	0
	2.4 Chemical engineering	0
	2.5 Materials engineering	0
	2.6 Medical engineering	0
	2.7 Environmental engineering	1
	2.8 Environmental biotechnology	0
	2.9 Industrial biotechnology	0
	2.10 Nano-technology	0
	2.11 Other engineering and technologies	21
	Total	23
3. Medical and Health Sciences	3.1 Basic medicine	4
	3.2 Clinical medicine	0
	3.3 Health sciences	1
	3.4 Medical biotechnology	0
	3.5 Other medical sciences	1
	Total	6
4. Agricultural sciences	4.1 Agriculture, Forestry, and Fisheries	2
	4.2 Animal and Dairy science	0
	4.3 Veterinary science	0

	4.4 Agricultural biotechnology	0
	4.5 Other agricultural sciences	1
	Total	3
5. Social sciences	5.1 Psychology	0
	5.2 Economics and Business	0
	5.3 Educational sciences	0
	5.4 Sociology	0
	5.5 Law	0
	5.6 Political science	0
	5.7 Social and economic geography	1
	5.8 Media and communications	0
	5.9 Other social sciences	5
	Total	6
6. Humanities	6.1 History and Archaeology	0
	6.2 Languages and Literature	1
	6.3 Philosophy, Ethics and Religion	0
	6.4 Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)	0
	6.5 Other humanities	0
	Total	1